

MIX-MATTERS

From Waste to Wealth

Agrifood Industry generates

113Mt/y
of mixed
bio-waste

75%
incinerated/
landfilled

3%
of total EU
GHG emissions

Greenhouses

Wholesale Market

Food & Drink Industry

SOURCE

Mixed bio-waste from three agri-food sectors.

Bioactive compounds

Powder ingredients

Sugar concentrates

Recombinant proteins

Green fibres

Plastic Monomers

Expected impacts

Avoid landfilling/incineration of **6.240 t/y** of mixed biowaste

Recycled **1.123 t/y** of plastic

Avoid the emission of **2.780 t/y** of CO₂

18 new value chains and **6 high value-added products**

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